

TRANSVERSE STRENGTH OF UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES WITH POLYESTER / URETHANE
ACRYLATE BLENDS AS MATRICES. A STUDY OF STRENGTH-REDUCTION MODELS.

M A Girardi* and M G Phillips

School of Materials Science, University of Bath, Bath BA2 7AY, U.K.

*Now with The Welding Institute, Abington Hall, Cambridge, CB1 6AL, U.K.

ABSTRACT

Blends of an isophthalic polyester (PE) with a poly(urethane acrylate) (UA) have been characterised over a wide range of compositions, to assess their potential value as matrices for glass-fibre composites. This paper compares the yield strengths of blends in the cast condition with the transverse tensile strengths of unidirectional glass-fibre composites incorporating the same blends as matrices.

In the cast condition, blends with up to 20% UA have strengths the same as, or higher than, PE. Further additions of UA produce a progressive reduction in yield strength, with accompanying increase in failure strain. Young's modulus of PE shows no significant reduction up to 5% addition of UA. At higher levels there is a progressive decrease in stiffness.

In unidirectional composites with glass volume fraction around 30%, transverse tensile strength (T_t) with a particular blend as matrix is, as expected, much below the yield strength of the blend (T_m). However, T_t varies only slowly with composition at UA contents up to 50%, so that the weakening effect of fibres appears to diminish as matrix strength and stiffness decline.

This observation is the basis for a critical examination of some published models for the strength reduction process. Their predictions are examined in a system where the relative stiffness of fibre and matrix varies, instead of the more usual variable, fibre volume fraction. Simple models based on the work of Greszczuk and of Kies, are shown to be unable to account for the observed variations. The model proposed by Cooper and Kelly can be adjusted to fit the data by using the "fibre-matrix bond strength" as a disposable parameter, but this suggests at some compositions a negative bond strength, which is difficult to understand. An approach to improving the Cooper / Kelly model is suggested.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Polymer blends; Testing/Evaluation; Transverse strength; Strength-reduction models.

1. INTRODUCTION

Unidirectional fibre composites with matrices of thermosetting polymer have high specific strength and stiffness when loaded in the fibre direction, but these properties are significantly lower in the transverse direction. Transverse stresses arise from complex loading, and although they may be minimised by careful design of structures, they cannot be entirely eliminated. There is therefore considerable interest in methods to improve the transverse strength of unidirectional composites.

One active area of research is the insertion of a compliant interphase between fibre and matrix (1). This is the subject of another paper from the authors' group at this conference (2) and will not be considered here.

An alternative approach has been to seek improved ductility, and/or fracture surface energy of the matrix material in bulk, while retaining as far as possible the original values of the associated properties: stiffness, glass-transition temperature, and heat-distortion temperature. The replacement of thermoset matrices with thermoplastics has met with some success in the aerospace composites field, but is at present of less interest for the general engineering market, because of material costs and the need to re-equip for a different technology.

The most widely employed technique of toughening composite matrices is to "modify" the thermoset by a dispersion of elastomer particles (3,4). For epoxy matrices, rubber modification is now virtually an industry standard, but for polyesters, where the kinetics of cure are different, it is sometimes less easy to obtain satisfactory dispersions of elastomer particles (5). As an alternative, use has recently been made of polyester / poly(urethane acrylate) blends to improve resistance to matrix cracking in critical locations such as joints in GRP structures (6). The authors' research has involved a study of the properties and constitution of blends in one PE/UA system, with the object of determining the conditions which give rise to toughening or flexibilisation. This paper compares the transverse strengths of unidirectional glass-fibre composites incorporating selected blends, with the yield strengths of the same blends in bulk. As is invariably found in such comparisons, the transverse strengths are much the lower. This observation forms the basis for a discussion of published models which seek to quantify the effect.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The resin used as a basis for the experimental blends was an isophthalic polyester formulated for high-performance applications (7). The second component was an unsaturated urethane acrylate (6). Both were kindly supplied by Scott Bader Co. Ltd of Wollaston, U.K. The components were presented as solutions in styrene, compatible in all proportions, and were cured at room temperature using a combination of cobalt accelerator and amine catalyst in a constant proportion for all blend compositions. Plaques of 3mm thickness were prepared by casting between glass plates, and allowed to cure for 24 hours before demoulding.

Tensile testpieces to I.S.O. Recommendation 527, Type 1, were machined from the plaques, and tested, with a minimum of five replications, at a crosshead speed of 5mm per minute in a screw-driven testing machine, with non-contact extensometer.

For the preparation of composites, use was made of a unidirectional mat, kindly supplied by Heinsco Ltd of Rochdale, U.K. (8). Instead of using rovings bound by transverse strands, this product contains parallel

filaments closely packed in a flat, crimp free sheet, held in position by a fine "spider's web" of polymer fibrils. On wetting out, the binder dissolves, leaving a truly unidirectional reinforcement. The mats used were of E glass with a superficial weight of 300g/sq.m. Eight layers were incorporated in laminates 3mm thick, the mats being individually wet out by hand, stacked, and finally pressed to size against stops. This produced a fairly consistent fibre volume fraction, as may be seen from Table 1, although the more viscous UA-rich blends were more difficult to incorporate. As with the castings, curing was for 24 hours at room temperature.

Testpieces for the transverse tensile test were parallel-sided strips of 25mm width, cut by diamond saw. The edges were carefully polished before testing, to remove any discontinuities. Test conditions were as for the cast plaques. Fibre volume fractions were determined by the burn-off method, using samples 25mm by approximately 50mm.

3. RESULTS

Table 1 shows the compositions of all blends investigated, with mean values of yield stress and initial tangent modulus for the cast materials. Columns four and five show the blends selected for composite manufacture, with their respective fibre volume fractions and mean transverse tensile strengths. The figures in brackets are 95% confidence limits about the means.

In the cast condition, UA additions of 5% and 10% appear to increase the strength of PE, although there is appreciable scatter in the strength values for 0% and 5% UA. Allowing for scatter, it can certainly be claimed that blends with up to 20% UA have strengths at least equal to the unmodified polyester. Thereafter, there is a progressive decrease in strength with increasing UA content. For Young's modulus, again taking account of scatter in the results, it may be stated that there is no significant change until 10% UA is reached, after which a progressive decrease occurs.

The transverse strengths of the composites show a quite remarkable consistency across a wide range of compositions, with appreciable decrease only at 80% and 100% UA. Mean strength values for both blends and composites are plotted as a function of composition in Figure 1. This emphasises that the reduction in strength caused by the introduction of transverse fibres is much less severe in matrices of lower initial strength and stiffness. This observation prompted a critical examination of some models which have been proposed to quantify the effect.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Models relating composite transverse strength to matrix strength.

The transverse strength of unidirectional composites is commonly observed to be much lower than the strength of the corresponding matrix material in the bulk. Published models which attempt to account for this have concentrated on the influence of fibre volume fraction (VF) in composite systems with a common matrix, such that the matrix stiffness (E_m) and strength (T_m) remain constant. The transverse strength (T_t) is then related to T_m via a stress concentration factor, defined as

$$S = T_m/T_t \quad (1)$$

4.1.1 Kies model Kies (9) approached this problem by calculating the strain magnification factor (eMF) for the matrix between fibres, by comparison with the average transverse strain in the composite. The equation defining eMF is:

$$e_{MF} = (\text{local matrix strain})/(\text{average transverse strain}) = e_m/e_t \quad (2)$$

Since composite failure is stated to occur when the matrix between fibres reaches its failure strain e_m^* , it follows that Equation 2 may be written in terms of the composite transverse failure strain e_t^* , as:

$$e_{MF} = e_m^*/e_t^* \quad (3)$$

If resin behaviour is elastic up to the point of fracture, then $T_m = E_m \cdot e_m^*$ and $T_t = E_t \cdot e_t^*$. Hence, from (1) and (3):

$$S = E_m \cdot e_m^*/E_t \cdot e_t^* = (E_m/E_t) \cdot e_{MF} \quad (4)$$

Kies equation is of the form:

$$e_{MF} = 1/(1 - (\text{SQR}(4VF/\pi))(1 - E_m/E_f)) \quad (5)$$

where SQR indicates "square root", $\pi = 3.1416$, and E_f is the transverse Young's modulus of the fibre.

For comparison with other models, it is convenient to combine (4) and (5) and invert, making the subject a "strength reduction factor", $1/S$. The substitutions: $X = \text{SQR}(4VF/\pi)$ and $R = E_m/E_f$ simplify the equation to give:

$$1/S(K) = (E_t/E_m)(1 - (1 - R) \cdot X) \quad (6)$$

where (K) denotes Kies' model. This quantity may be evaluated using experimentally-determined moduli for matrix and composite.

4.1.2 Greszczuk's model Where the matrix modulus is constant, the ratio E_t/E_m in equation (6) may be expressed as a function of VF by one of several equations. Greszczuk (10) used the Reuss, or plates-in-series, model:

$$1/E_t = VF/E_f + (1-VF)/E_m \quad (7)$$

Making this substitution in equation (6) the Greszczuk model is represented by:

$$1/S(G) = \frac{1 - (1 - R)(\pi/4)X^2}{1 - X(1 - R)} \quad (8)$$

4.1.3 The Cooper/Kelly model Cooper and Kelly (12) give an expression for the transverse strength of a composite which takes into account, on the one hand, weakening by the reduction in effective area of matrix as VF increases, and on the other, the contribution of the fibre/matrix bond, which increases with VF. In the terms employed here, this may be written:

$$T_t = T_m(1 - X) + T'X \quad (9)$$

where T' is the mean stress required to separate fibres from matrix. Dividing by T_m , and defining the "C-K parameter", f , by: $f = T'/T_m$, we obtain:

$$1/S(C) = 1 - X + fX = 1 - (1 - f)X \quad (10)$$

4.2 Comparison between the models In Figure 2, these three models are compared by plotting $1/S$ as a function of X , the volume fraction term. Since the Kies model can be evaluated only where E_m and E_t are known, we have plotted in Figure 2A, $(E_m/E_t)(1/S)$, which is, of course, the inverse of Kies' original strain magnification factor e_{MF} . Variations in matrix properties influence this model only via the ratio R , which is equal to E_m/E_f . Figure 2A shows two curves with values of R bracketing the range obtainable with real composites, ie 0.1 and 0.01, and it will be seen that the predictions of the model are very little affected by this change.

Figure 2B shows the non-linear variation obtained by plotting equation (8), the Greszczuk model. Here again, only the ratio R incorporates matrix properties, and as above, the two values 0.1 and 0.01 have been used for illustration. There is an appreciable divergence of the curves only at high volume fractions. The limiting VF for fibres in a square array is represented by $X = 1$.

Figure 2C illustrates the Cooper and Kelly model, equation (10). Evidently this is a straight line of slope $(1 - f)$. Of the two terms involved in " f ", T_m can be directly measured, but T' is unknown. Thus, it seems reasonable to treat f as a disposable parameter, and obtain values of T' by fitting to experimental results. The two curves corresponding to extreme values of f are shown by the bold lines in Figure 2C. The condition $f = 0$ corresponds to zero bond strength between fibre and matrix, such that the strength reduction factor is simply equal to the proportion by area of resin in the composite cross-section, ie, to $(1 - X)$. The condition $f = 1$ implies no reduction in strength by the introduction of glass fibres, so that this line is horizontal. Evidently, the Cooper / Kelly model, unlike the other two, is capable of accomodating wide variations in strength reduction factor at a given VF.

4.3 Comparison of strength-reduction models with experimental results.

Measured strength reduction factors T_t/T_m for selected blends, taken from the curves in Figure 1, are plotted in Figure 2 as functions of X . It will be seen that the scatter in VF for the experimental laminates was very small. For Figure 2A, the measured values have been converted to $1/e_{MF}$ via equation (4).

It is obvious that neither the Kies nor the Greszczuk model is capable of representing composite behaviour where matrix modulus and strength vary over a wide range. We shall therefore apply the Cooper/Kelly model to determine the experimental values of f , and hence of T' , as functions of matrix composition. It may then be possible to rationalise the observed strength properties.

Inspection of equation (10) shows that where $X = 1$, then $f = 1/S$, so that it is easy to determine the value of f to match an experimental point in Figure 2C by extrapolating the line from $(0,1)$ through the point, and reading off its intersection with the line $X = 1$. This process is illustrated by the middle line in Figure 2C, where the indicated value is $f = 0.46$. Values of f have been determined for all the composites included in Figure 1. When multiplied by the corresponding matrix strength, they give the empirical values of T' for those composites, which are plotted in Figure 3 as a function of matrix composition. The first observation to be made is that in several cases T' appears to be negative, a curious result which arises because in Figure 2C the majority of experimental points fall below the line $f = 0$. Secondly, there is no consistent trend in these values with composition, though it may be noted that values are positive at the higher UA contents. If this means anything, it may be taken to imply an improvement in bonding with UA content, which is consistent with the known adhesive characteristics of this material.

A more justifiable conclusion is that the model is inadequate, because the factors determining transverse strength cannot be incorporated in a single parameter. An obvious modification would be to introduce a second parameter to represent, for example, the weakening effect of residual shrinkage stresses in the matrix. T' would then represent the balance between two opposing tendencies, so that negative values would be acceptable. To quantify this one might assume as a first approximation, a constant shrinkage strain across all blend compositions. The level of residual stress from this cause would decrease with increasing UA content, in proportion to the observed decrease in Young's modulus (Table 1). There would therefore be a shift of the balance in the same direction as would be promoted by improved fibre/matrix adhesion.

Experimental verification of such a model would require composites with a range of fibre volume fractions in each matrix blend, which were not to hand at the time of writing.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The factors governing the transverse strength of a unidirectional composite are complex, and existing "strength-reduction" models are inadequate to represent them. This work has suggested a possible route towards improving understanding in this area.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The work described here was financed by a CASE studentship awarded by the Science and Engineering Research Council of the U.K., with GKN Technology Ltd of Wolverhampton, U.K., as Co-operating Body.

7. REFERENCES

1. L. D. Tryson and J. L. Kardos, 36th Annual Technical Conference, Reinforced Plastics/Composites Institute, Society of the Plastics Industry, Section 2E, 1981.
2. K. R. J. Ellis and M. G. Phillips, Proceedings, ICCM8, 1991.
3. E. H. Rowe, *ibid.* reference 1, 34th Conference, Section 23B, 1979.
4. P. D. Tetlow, J. F. Mandell, and F. J. McGarry, *ibid.* reference 3, Section 23F, 1979.
5. G. A. Crosbie and M. G. Phillips, *J. Materials Sci.*, 20, 563-577, 1985.
6. "Crestomer 1080" Product data, Scott Bader Co, Wollaston, U.K., 1985.
7. "Crystic 272" Product data, Scott Bader Co, Wollaston, U.K., 1978.
8. G. Heins, *ibid.* reference 1, 42nd Conference, Section 7B, 1987.
9. J. A. Kies, "Maximum strains in the resin of fibre glass composites". U.S. Naval Research Laboratory Report NRL 5752, 1962.
10. L. B. Greszczuk, *ibid.* reference 1, 21st Conference, Section 8A, 1966.
11. G. A. Cooper & A. Kelly, ASTM Special Technical Publication No 452, 90, 1969.

TABLE 1

Tensile properties of polyester/urethane-acrylate blends, and transverse strength of unidirectional composites made from them. Figures in brackets are 95% confidence limits.

Blend Composition % UA	CAST BLENDS		COMPOSITES			
	Yield Stress Tm (MPa)	Young's Modulus Em (GPa)	Fibre vol. fraction VF	Transverse Strength Tt (MPa)	Transverse Modulus Et (GPa)	
0	61.0 (3.9)	3.46 (0.24)	0.35 (0.03)	17.3 (0.9)	9.5 (0.8)	
5	70.0 (6.3)	3.55 (0.54)	0.35 (0.03)	18.0 (1.0)	7.4 (0.5)	
10	70.0 (1.1)	3.17 (0.11)	0.34 (0.03)	17.8 (0.7)	6.2 (0.7)	
15	64.5 (5.0)	3.08 (0.13)	0.32 (0.03)	16.9 (0.7)	6.0 (0.2)	
20	60.5 (0.3)	2.88 (0.06)	0.30 (0.03)	18.4 (0.6)	5.4 (0.8)	
25	54.0 (0.8)	2.85 (0.29)	0.30 (0.03)	16.6 (0.6)	5.0 (0.3)	
40	46.8 (0.6)	2.35 (0.03)	-	-	-	
50	41.2 (0.2)	1.80 (0.08)	0.31 (0.03)	17.0 (0.9)	3.4 (0.2)	
60	33.0 (0.2)	1.65 (0.10)	-	-	-	
80	21.5 (1.0)	1.35 (0.01)	0.31 (0.03)	14.3 (0.7)	1.4 (0.1)	
100	14.9 (2.2)	0.99 (0.02)	0.30 (0.03)	7.9 (0.2)	0.8 (0.1)	

Figure 1. Effect of composition on yield strength of PE/UA blends, and on transverse tensile strength of unidirectional fibre composites made from them.

Figure 2. "Strength reduction factors" for transverse strength of unidirectional composites as a function of fibre volume fraction.

A. Kies' model (Failure strain reduction factor).

B. Greszczuk's model.

C. Model of Cooper and Kelly.

Circles show experimental points from the present work.

Figure 3. Apparent "fibre-matrix bond strength" for unidirectional composites, as a function of matrix composition.

